

Research in Sensorless Vector Control of Induction Motor based on MRAS Technique

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Abstract—Model Reference Adaptive System (MRAS) represents one of the most attractive and popular solutions for sensorless control of AC drive. According to the principle of asynchronous motor vector control, taking two phase rotating coordinates current model as the adjustable model and improved voltage model as reference model, a speed sensorless vector control system is built. The model reference adaptive system (MRAS) method is used to identify system speed. Model reference adaptive system method is applied to asynchronous motor speed estimation and achieves speed sensorless control of asynchronous motor. The approach is implemented on Matlab /Simulink software. The simulation results show that the system has good control performance and accuracy. It proves the feasibility and practicability of the system.

Keywords—motor; speed sensorless, model reference adaptive system, SVPWM, vector control

I. INTRODUCTION

This With the continuous improvement of power electronics technology and control theory, pay flow motor speed control system increasingly towards high performance. Ac asynchronous power machine speed sensorless speed control system to speed identification algorithm instead of sensing the speed of the detection device, to avoid speed sensor detection errors caused poor and sensor installation and maintenance of the difficulties, and has the price the advantages of the project has an important application of significance, is a modern communication important research direction. In induction motor speed sensorless control technology, the motor turns speed identification method after

another, such as: extended kalman filter [1-4] neural network [5-8], pi adaptive method[9-11] and so on. The model reference is self-adaptive the theory of MRAS (model reference adaptive system)[12-14] is in recent years, speed sensorless induction motor vector control more good application of speed identification technology, which is characterized by guaranteed parameter estimation the gradual stability of the same time, changes in motor parameters and external disturbances has strong robustness. With the microcontroller, digital signal processor such as the continuous improvement of microprocessor performance, MRAS speed identification technology in the field of speed sensorless ac speed has a very good application prospect.

In this paper, the speed sensorless motor control, the introduction of model parameters Self-adaptive speed identification theory, through the rotor speed estimation the system can accurately identify the actual speed, the experimental results verify the propose a strategy of feasibility and effectiveness.

A. Vector Control System

a. Control System Program

The system measures the current i_A , i_B from the stator side of the motor And voltage u_A , u_B , Converted to is_α , is_β by Clarke And us_α , us_β , Into the rotor fluxThe observer model calculates rotor flux linkage angle and flux linkage values. The actual rotation of the motor The speed n is obtained by MRAS model estimation, according to the speed command value n_{ref} And the difference between the feedback value n , the speed regulator output corresponding electromagnetic torque The current value of the component i_s^Tref , And then with the system given excitation current component i_s^{Mref} $U_s^T ref$ through the current regulator together And us^{Mref} , through Park inverse transform voltage $us_\alpha ref$ This scheme can make the torque and flux completely decoupled, very good To estimate the motor speed, speed, current closed-loop control.

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Figure 1. Speed sensorless vector control system block diagram

b. Rotor flux Observer

In the sensorless vector control [15], rotor flux linkage observation is Sub-important. Using the voltage model as a reference model, the current model can be adjusted Model of the program to calculate the flux linkage.

Flux Linkage Model:

Stator current by 3s / 2r transform excitation componentism And the torque component i_{st} , the motor vector control equation is

$$T_e = n_p \frac{L_m}{L_r} i_{st} \psi_r \quad (1)$$

$$\omega_s = \frac{L_m i_{st}}{T_r \psi_r} \quad (2)$$

$$\psi_r = \frac{L_m}{T_r p + 1} i_{sm} \quad (3)$$

Where, T_e For torque; L_m For mutual inductance; L_r For the rotor inductance; ψ_r For the rotor Flux; i_{st} is the torque current component; T_r For the time constant. According to formula (1) ~ (3) can calculate the motor slip frequency ω_s , the stator current frequency ω_1 ($\omega_1 = \omega_s + \omega_r$) and ψ_r [4]. The two-phase rotating coordinate system rotor flux linkage model can be adjusted Model to stator current and speed ω_r As an input to calculate the rotor flux, the mathematical model as shown in (4), (5) below.

$$\psi_\alpha = \frac{L_m}{T_r} i_\alpha - \frac{\psi_\alpha}{T_r} - \omega_r \psi_\beta \quad (4)$$

$$\psi_\beta = \frac{L_m}{T_r} i_\beta - \frac{\psi_\beta}{T_r} - \omega_r \psi_\alpha \quad (5)$$

Compared with two-phase stationary coordinate flux model, two-phase rotation coordinate Flux model more suitable for computer real-time computing, easy convergence, more accurate. Indeed However, Eqs. (4) and (5) also show that the

current and speed are used as input. The current model relies heavily on the rotor Tr. If Tr, there is deviation, will directly lead to the magnetic field is not allowed to be allowed to cause rotation between the axis of the system. Strong coupling, so the current model cannot be used alone without speed sensing. Vector control, the need to use together with the voltage model [5].

B. Fundamentals

Asynchronous motor vector control theory, is to produce the same spin. The stator current i_A, i_B, i_C in the three-phase coordinate system are the criterion. By 3s / 2s transformation, can be equivalent to two-phase static coordinate system under the electricity flow i_α, i_β . And then through the synchronous rotation transformation, the motor stator current

Figure 2. Vector control schematic

c. Mathematical model of asynchronous motor

From the asynchronous motor in the three-phase coordinate system can be seen in the mathematical model. The motor is multivariable, non-linear, strongly coupled system. To obtain the speed-regulating performance similar to that of DC motor, vector control must be carried out. Mathematics of Asynchronous motor in two-phase synchronous d-q coordinate system model.

Voltage Equation:

Stator Voltage Equation

$$\left. \begin{aligned} u_{ds} &= R_s i_{ds} + \frac{d\varphi_{ds}}{dt} - \varphi_{qs} \frac{d\theta_s}{dt} \\ u_{qs} &= R_s i_{qs} + \frac{d\varphi_{qs}}{dt} + \varphi_{ds} \frac{d\theta_s}{dt} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (6)$$

Rotor Voltage Equation

$$\left. \begin{aligned} u_{dr} &= R_r i_{dr} + \frac{d\varphi_{dr}}{dt} - \varphi_{qr} \frac{d\theta_r}{dt} \\ u_{qr} &= R_r i_{qr} + \frac{d\varphi_{qr}}{dt} + \varphi_{dr} \frac{d\theta_r}{dt} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (7)$$

Flux linkage equation:

Stator flux equation

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \varphi_{ds} &= L_s i_{ds} + L_m i_{dr} \\ \varphi_{qs} &= L_s i_{qs} + L_m i_{qr} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (8)$$

Rotor flux equation

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \varphi_{dr} &= L_r i_{dr} + L_m i_{ds} \\ \varphi_{qr} &= L_r i_{qr} + L_m i_{qs} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (9)$$

Torque equation

$$T = \rho L_m (i_{qs} i_{ds} - i_{qr} i_{dr}) \quad (10)$$

decomposition. Into each other perpendicular to the excitation current i_m . And torque current i_t . When observing. Standing on the core, and with the coordinate system with the rotation, the AC motor will be equivalent. Become a DC motor, it can imitate the DC motor control method to achieve the control of asynchronous motor. Among them, the AC motor rotor total magnetic flux ψ_r . It becomes equivalent to the DC motor flux, M winding is equivalent to DC motor excitation winding, i_m Equivalent to the excitation current, T winding quite. In the static winding, i_t Equivalent to the armature current proportional to the torque. To. On these equivalence relations can be expressed in Figure 1, the figure i_A, i_B, i_C for Three-phase AC input, ω_r For speed output.

In the above formula, $u_{ds}, u_{qs}, u_{dr}, u_{qr}$ Respectively, set, the rotor voltage d - q axis component; $i_{ds}, i_{qs}, i_{dr}, i_{qr}$ Respectively, the rotor current d - q axis Component; $\varphi_{qs}, \varphi_{dr}, \varphi_{qr}$ Respectively, fixed, rotor flux d - q axis points Quantity; L_r For the d - q coordinate system, the rotor is equivalent to the two - phase winding Feeling; For the d - q coordinate system between the stator and the rotor coaxial equivalent winding Mutation; p is the differential operator; θ is the rotor a axis and $\alpha - \beta$ coordinate system α The angle between the axes; ω_r For the rotor angular velocity, $\omega_r = d\theta / dt$; θ_s For the d axis with Two - phase stationary $\alpha - \beta$ coordinate system α axis between the angle; ω_s Rotate for the stator Magnetic field synchronous angular velocity, $\omega_s = d\theta_s / dt$; θ_r For the d axis and the rotor a axis

The angle of $\theta_r = \theta_s - \theta$.

II. MODEL REFERENCE ADAPTIVE SYSTEM DESIGN

The model reference adaptive speed[16,17] is calculated using the rotor flux. The pressure equation and the current equation are respectively calculated for the rotor flux due to the voltage model Does not contain the speed signal, while the

current model contains the speed signal, so the voltage model As the output of the rotor flux, the current model of the output as The calculated value of the rotor flux, to calculate the motor speed. Model Reference adaptive principle shown in Figure 2, Figure 3 shows.

Figure 3. Model reference adaptive angular velocity identification algorithm

Figure 4. MRAS angular velocity identification algorithm with filter link

As the MRAS shown in Figure 2 is prone to error accumulation and DC Offset problem, so the traditional MRAS to improve, as shown in Figure 3. After the improved algorithm, to a certain extent, can improve the pure integral band To the impact of the choice of adaptive law can make the system gradually stable

III. SIMULATION SYSTEM

A. Simulation Model

This paper is based on Matlab/ simulink for Asynchronous motor MRAS the speed calculation system is simulated and simulated induction motor parameters show in table1 .

Parameters	Values
Stator resistance(Rs)	0.435Ω
Rotor resistance(Rr)	0.816Ω

Figure 6. Estimated speed

Figure 7. Actual speed

At a given speed of 0.26 s and a load of 0.6 s, the system regulator And the torque has a corresponding response. The rotor speed is at t = 0.26 s at start-up Has stabilized state, the stator flux at the start of a large change, electricity The

magnetic torque has overshoot at the start and the given speed command change, but soon Tends to be stable, the stator flux amplitude gradually becomes constant, the system estimates the

Figure 8. Estimated and actual speed at the same coordinate

Figure 11. Estimated speed

Figure 12. Actual speed

At a given speed of 0.26 s and a load of 0.6 s, the system regulator And the torque has a corresponding response. The rotor speed is at $t = 0.26$ s at start-up Has stabilized state, the stator flux at the start of a large change, electricity The

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Figure 13. Estimated and actual speed at the same coordinate

Figure 14. Motor output torque

Figure 16 to Figure 19 are simulated according to the simulation model shown in Figure 15 Simulation results shown. System given speed of 150 r / min, no load start, in the

vector Under control, the speed rise steadily, after loading, a slight decline but then recovered.

Figure 15. System simulation Model

Figure 16. Estimated speed

Figure 17. Actual speed

At a given speed of 0.26 s and a load of 0.6 s, the system regulator and the torque has a corresponding response. The rotor speed is at $t = 0.26$ s at start-up has stabilized state, the stator flux at the start of a large change, electricity The

magnetic torque has overshoot at the start and the given speed command change, but soon Tends to be stable, the stator flux amplitude gradually becomes constant, the system estimates the

Figure 18. Estimated and actual speed at the same coordinate

Figure 19. motor output torque

CONCLUSION

Neural network has a certain degree of ascension, can be considered as a control System strategy applied to the practical application. While the reality of the car temperature in the fine The degree does not need to do very high, mainly taking into account the cost of research and development. This limits the application of neural network control in the car, but according to the future The direction of development, people for the comfort and rapid response requirements are not Improve the control, neural network control will have a great development prospects

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